

ISic3247

I.Sicily inscription 3247

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Matthew Pawlowski,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 434

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus) [s(acrum)]

2. Nasidia Epity[nchanu]

3. sa · vixit · an(nis)[---]

Apparatus

Text of Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Sacred to the Shades of the Underworld. Nasidia Epitynchanusa lived for [---] years

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493977

EDR 139175

EDCS 22200397

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a

l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. At 2004.0650

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 112

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